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Legal Research Methodology: Frameworks For Literature Review Under The NALT Guide

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ABSTRACT

Literature review is an important component of every research. It helps the researcher to be abreast with current literature on the research topic. It also acquaints the researcher with the main concepts, theories, methodologies, methods, findings and current debates in the research area. However, most researchers now see the literature review as a mere summary of literature without critiquing the existing literature. The aim of this paper is to examine the frameworks for literature review under the Nigerian Association of Law Teachers (NALT) Guide. It examines the concept and sources of literature. It also examines the concept of theory and distinguishes between general theories of law and special theories of law for the review of literature. It further examines the process of literature review and identification of gap in knowledge. It adopts the doctrinal research methodology. It relies on secondary data. It found that nowadays literature reviews are poorly written as annotated bibliographies without any analysis of the relationship amongst the existing literature, evaluation of their strengths and weaknesses and synthesis of the findings and contributions of other scholars to the research topic. It suggests that researchers should conduct literature review at two levels to produce quality research report on any subject matter.

Keywords: Gap in Knowledge, Literature Critiquing, Literature Search, Literature Review

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The term **literature** refers to both published and unpublished materials on a specific research topic.¹ It is any previous study carried out by any scholar on a topic related to the present research. It consists of all written sources relevant to the topic or the phenomenon under investigation.² It refers to scholarly sources such as journal articles, books, theses and dissertations related to the research topic. A review of such related literature is central to any research. It helps the researcher to be abreast with the state-of-art knowledge of the topic. It also acquaints the researcher with the main concepts, theories, methodologies, methods, findings and current debates in the research area.³

However, nowadays literature reviews are poorly written as annotated bibliographies without any analysis of the relationship amongst the existing literature, evaluation of their strengths and weaknesses and synthesis of the findings and contributions of other scholars to the research topic. Most researchers see the literature review as mere descriptive summaries of literature without conducting any deeper analysis.⁴

The aim of this paper is to examine the frameworks for literature review under the Nigerian Association Law Teachers (NALT) *Uniform Format and Citation Guide for Legal Writing*.⁵ It examines the concept and sources of literature. It also examines the nature and types of literature review. It further examines the concept of theory and distinguishes between general theories of law

¹ Joshua J Mark, *World History Encyclopedia* (2009) <<http://www.worldhistory.org/literature>> accessed 16 August 2024; HC Klopper, 'The Qualitative Research Proposal' [2008] *Curationis* 62, 64.

² HC Klopper, 'The Qualitative Research Proposal' [2008] *Curationis* 62, 64.

³ JJ Randolf, 'A Guide to Writing the Dissertation Literature Review' [2009] 14(3) *Practical Assessment Research and Evaluation* 1, 2.

⁴ Hannah Snyder, 'Literature Review as a Research Methodology: An Overview and Guidelines' [2019] 104 *Journal of Business Research* 333-339, 338.

⁵ Nigerian Association of Law Teachers, *NALT Uniform Format and Citation Guide for Legal Writing* (NALT 2021) (hereinafter simply referred to as "the NALT Guide").

and special theories of law for the review of literature. Finally, it examines the process of literature review and identification of gap in the literature.

The paper adopts the doctrinal research methodology. It relies on secondary data. It found that nowadays literature reviews are poorly written as annotated bibliographies without any analysis of the relationship amongst the existing literature, evaluation of their strengths and weaknesses and synthesis of the findings and contributions of other scholars to the research topic. It offers suggestions for conducting literature review that would produce quality research report on any subject matter.

2.0 Sources of Literature

The **main sources of literature** are: articles in peer-reviewed journals such as academic or scholarly journals, professional journals and trade journals; chapters in reference books; textbooks, monographs, encyclopaedias and dictionaries; unpublished materials such as seminar papers, conference proceedings, theses and dissertations; and internet materials.⁶

Textbooks written by authoritative authors and published by reputable publishers in the discipline are useful literature because they generally contain a summary of current ideas on a topic. However, they can quickly become outdated. On the other hand, journals provide current and up-to-date literature that allows the researcher to view the current state of the topic in terms of research and development.⁷ Thus, articles in journals should form the core of the literature review.⁸

Other sources of literature are government publications (also known as “grey literature”) and articles in nationally and internationally recognized newspapers and magazines.⁹ The term **grey literature** is not limited to government publications. It refers generally to any material that is not published by a mainstream publisher and therefore difficult to obtain.¹⁰ Thus, grey literature includes government publications, company reports, theses and dissertations, conference proceedings, trade journals and magazines, newspapers, leaflets and posters, media reports, maps, music, diaries, letters, patents and other legal documents.¹¹

3.0 Contexts for Literature Review:

There are three main **contexts for literature review**. It may be a component part of a research report such as a section in an article in a peer-reviewed journal or a chapter in a thesis or dissertation.¹² It may be an end in itself, that is, as a stand-alone review such as a review article in a journal. It may be part of a preliminary stage in larger research study such as an academic research proposal or a research grant proposal.¹³

In whatever context it may be required, it is not necessary for the researcher to discuss every literature that he has read. The discussion should be limited to those studies that have a direct bearing on the central focus of his research. In addition, the literature review should not be a mere summary of what every scholar has said about the subject matter of the research. It should focus only on the aspects of those studies that are relevant to his research topic.¹⁴ It should present the most significant and relevant studies on the subject matter in a logical and systematic manner, their methods and major findings and demonstrate how his research will resolve these issues.¹⁵

⁶ Andrew S Denny and Richard Tewksbury, ‘How to Write a Literature Review’ [2012] *Journal of Criminal Justice Education* 1, 10; Diana Ridley, *The Literature Review: A Step-by-Step Guide for Students* (2nd edn, SAGE Publications Ltd 2012) 43-44.

⁷ F Timmins and C McCabe, ‘How to Conduct an Effective Literature Search’ [2005] 20(11) *Nursing Standard* 41, 46.

⁸ Jennifer Rowley and Frances Slack, ‘Conducting a Literature Review’ [2004] 27 *Management Research News* 31-39, 32.

⁹ Andrew S Denny and Richard Tewksbury, ‘How to Write a Literature Review’ [2012] *Journal of Criminal Justice Education* 1, 10-11.

¹⁰ Andrea Heath, Paul Levay and Daniel Tuvey, ‘Literature Searching Methods or Guidance and Their Application to Public Health Topics: A Narrative Review’ [2021] *Health Information and Library Journal* 1, 6; Amanda Bolderston, ‘Writing an Effective Literature Review’ [2008] 39 *Journal of Medical Imaging and Radiation Sciences* 86, 88.

¹¹ Diana Ridley, *The Literature Review: A Step-by-Step Guide for Students* (2nd edn, SAGE Publications Ltd 2012) 45-46.

¹² Jeffrey W Knopf, ‘Doing a Literature Review’ [2006] 39(1) *Political Science and Politics* 127.

¹³ See JL Galvan and MC Galvan, ‘Writing Literature Reviews: A Guide for Students of the Social and Behavioural Sciences’ (7th edn, Routledge 2017) 288.

¹⁴ Jeffrey W Knopf, ‘Doing a Literature Review’ [2006] 39(1) *Political Science and Politics* 127, 129.

¹⁵ P Cronin, F Ryan and M Coughlan, ‘Undertaking a Literature Review: A Step-by-Step Approach’ [2008] 17(1) *British Journal of Nursing* 38, 43.

4.0 Nature and Importance of Literature Review

Literature review is a critical evaluation of the documents containing ideas, concepts, theories and methodologies about the research topic. According to the American Psychological Association, it is an evaluation of existing literature by identifying relations, contradictions, gaps and inconsistencies in the literature and by suggesting the next step needed to solve the research problem.¹⁶ Therefore, literature review should not only summarize or report the claims made in the existing literature but also examine critically the research methods used to better understand whether the claims are warranted.¹⁷

The literature review affords the researcher the opportunity to demonstrate his knowledge about a particular field of study, including vocabulary, theories, key variables and phenomena, and its methods and history. It also informs the researcher of other influential researchers and research groups in the field.¹⁸ Finally, with some modification, the literature review is a legitimate and publishable scholarly document.¹⁹

The literature review enables the researcher to distinguish between what has been learned and accomplished in the area of study and what still needs to be learned and accomplished.²⁰ A good literature review is the basis of both theoretical and methodological sophistication, thereby improving the quality and usefulness of the present research.²¹

The literature review helps the researcher to identify any gaps in the literature relating to the problem and to suggest how those gaps might be filled. It should demonstrate an appropriate depth and breadth of reading around the topic in question. The majority of studies included should be of recent origin and ideally less than five years old.²² In other words, the literature reviewed should be **current literature**, that is, it should be state-of-the-art literature. It should not be some archaic or outdated literature beyond five years.²³ It should also be **relevant literature**, that is, it should be previous studies on the research topic or some aspects of the topic. It should not be some literature unrelated to the research topic.²⁴

5.0 Reasons for Literature Review

Apart from the reasons enumerated above for writing literature review (i.e. proof of knowledge, a publishable document, and the identification of a research family), there are many scientific **reasons for conducting a literature review**. They include the following amongst others:

- (1) **To appraise the state-of-the-art literature on the subject matter.** The literature review helps the researcher to become familiar with the current or most recent literature on the subject matter he intends to investigate. Research cannot be conducted in isolation of the existing literature on the topic. This is because research is cumulative; it must learn from and build on the existing research on the topic.²⁵
- (2) **To identify the gap in the literature.** The literature review helps the researcher to know what others have done on the topic and state what they have not done, so as to identify the gap in the literature, which will justify the current study.²⁶

¹⁶ American Psychological Association, *Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association: The Official Guide to the APA Style* (7th edn, American Psychological Association 2020) 427.

¹⁷ David N Boote and Penny Beile, 'Scholars Before Researchers: On the Centrality of Dissertation Literature Review in Research Preparation' [2005] 34(6) *Educational Researcher* 3, 4.

¹⁸ JJ Randolph, 'A Guide to Writing the Dissertation Literature Review' [2009] 14(3) *Practical Assessment Research and Evaluation* 1, 2.

¹⁹ Margaret D LeCompte and Others, 'Editors' Introduction' [2003] 73(20) *Review of Educational Research* 123, 124.

²⁰ Boote and Beile (n 17) 4.

²¹ Ibid 4.

²² M Coughlan, P Cronin and F Ryan, 'Step-by-Step Guide to Critiquing Research Part 1: Quantitative Research' [2007] 16(11) *British Journal of Nursing* 658, 660.

²³ Ibid 660.

²⁴ GG Otuturu, 'Legal Research Methodology: The Nuts and Bolts of Research Proposal' [2024] 4(2) *International Journal of Civil Law and Legal Research* 56-66

²⁵ Boote and Beile (n 17) 1.

²⁶ H Cooper and AC Koenka, 'The Overview of Reviews: Unique Challenges and Opportunities When Research Syntheses are the Principal Elements of New Integrative Scholarship' [2012] 67(6) *American Psychologist* 446-462.

- (3) **To gain a new perspective on the research topic.** The literature review helps the researcher to synthesize the existing literature to know how the subject matter has developed over time.²⁷ This will assist the researcher to acquire the appropriate vocabulary on the subject matter. It will also assist the researcher to introduce a new perspective to the topic. It is the researcher's perspective that brings originality to the topic. Thus, the researcher may introduce comparative or international perspective to distinguish his research from the existing literature on the topic.
- (4) **To ascertain a suitable methodology for the study.** The literature review will reveal the contributions that others have made to the pool of knowledge on the topic. This will provide the researcher with the framework for his own research including the methodologies, data collection techniques, key concepts and theories that have been used by others.²⁸ This will enable the researcher to determine appropriate methodology, concepts and theories to be used for the research.
- (5) **To define and limit the area of the research.** It is the literature review that will help the researcher to contextualize his research by situating it in the larger body of knowledge which provides the background and creates the gap for his research.²⁹ It will also help the researcher to limit the scope of his study by focusing on the gap the research intends to fill.

6.0 Types of Literature Review

There are two main types of literature review. These are systematic literature review, also known as evidence-based literature review, and narrative literature review, also known as non-systematic or traditional literature review. However, there are numerous other types of literature review especially in science, engineering, medical and health research. For example, there are other unique types of literature review such as methodological literature review, conceptual literature review, theoretical literature review, historical literature review, and integrative literature review amongst others.

Methodological literature review centres on the methods used for analysis and how the researcher arrived at a particular conclusion. **Theoretical literature review** identifies the existing theories and relates them to the specific study.³⁰ **Conceptual literature review** identifies and connects different concepts, ideas and variables that are relevant to the research topic; while **historical literature review** reconstructs or deconstructs the understanding of some past phenomenon or the development of a contemporary phenomenon through the lens of literature that captures historic forces.³¹ It is intended to examine systematic literature review, narrative literature review and integrative literature review in some detail.

6.1 Systematic Literature Review

Systematic literature review is a well-planned review to answer specific questions using explicit and rigorous criteria to identify, select and critically evaluate and synthesize all the literature on a particular topic. It details the time frame within which the literature was selected and the methods used to evaluate the findings of the studies in question.³²

The main objective of systematic literature review is to formulate a well-defined question and provide a quantitative or meta-analysis of the relevant evidence. There are specific reporting guidelines for systematic reviews known as PRIMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis).³³ It is suitable for empirical research especially in medical and health science, social science and management science.

²⁷ Chris Hart, *Doing a Literature Review: Releasing the Social Science Research Imagination* (SAGE Publications Ltd 1998) 27.

²⁸ Ibid 26-27.

²⁹ Diana Ridley, *The Literature Review: A Step-by-Step Guide for Students* (2nd edn, SAGE Publications Ltd 2012) 6.

³⁰ IS Mohammed, 'Problems of Academic Literature Review and Writing: The Way Forward' [2018] 16(5) *Journal of Management Sciences* 11, 17-18.

³¹ Jamie L Callahan, 'Constructing a Manuscript: Distinguishing Integrative Literature Reviews and Conceptual and Theory Articles' [2010] 9(3) *Human Resource Development Review* 300-304.

³² Patricia Cronin, Frances Ryan and Michael Coughlan, 'Undertaking a Literature Review: A Step-by-Step Approach' [2008] 17(1) *British Journal of Nursing* 38, 39.

³³ Rossella Ferrari, 'Writing Narrative Style Literature Reviews' [2015] 24(4) *Medical Writing* 230.

6.2 Narrative Literature Review

Narrative literature review provides a broad qualitative overview of a topic. It summarizes, analyzes and synthesizes existing literature on the topic. It is essentially qualitative, descriptive and interpretive. It does not follow any specific criteria for selection or exclusion of the literature. In other words, it is non-systematic and non-structured. The researcher selects the literature based on their relevance.³⁴

Narrative literature review can inspire new research ideas by identifying gaps and inconsistencies in the existing literature and thus help in defining research questions. It can also help in developing conceptual and theoretical frameworks.³⁵ It is suitable for qualitative research especially in law, arts and humanities.

6.3 Integrative Literature Review

Integrative literature review is a form of research that reviews, critiques and synthesizes representative literature on a topic. It has a methodology that clearly outlines *where* the literature was found, *when* the search was conducted, *who* conducted the search, *how* the literature was found, *what* number of articles were found, and *why* some articles were selected.³⁶ The literature may include both empirical and non-empirical literature.³⁷ It aims at building new knowledge based on a broad array of existing literature to address a particular phenomenon.³⁸

The best integrative reviews are those that examine the existing literature with focus on its objectives followed with critical evaluation and examination of the literature. It provides a clear conception of the research question and integrates the current and emerging ideas together. It enables the emergence of new models, conceptual frameworks and further enhances the understanding of the topic.³⁹ It is mostly used in nursing, healthcare, business and social sciences.

7.0 Frameworks for Literature Review

Under the NALT Guide, there are three **frameworks for literature review**. These are conceptual framework, theoretical framework and empirical framework or review of related literature on the subject matter of the research. Closely related to these frameworks is the historical foundation, or historical background, or historical development of the subject matter.

7.1 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework may be likened to the floor plan of a building showing such variables as doors, rooms, parlours, toilets and kitchen, and the relationship between the different variables. Applied to research, the **conceptual framework** lays out the key concepts or variables in the study and the relationship between them.⁴⁰

Under the conceptual framework, therefore, the researcher examines the relevant concepts in the research topic. In other words, the researcher defines and explains the different concepts and issues that make up the research topic. The importance of definitions cannot be overemphasized. They help to conceptualize ideas and give them precise meanings in the context of the research.⁴¹

³⁴ Patricia Cronin, Frances Ryan and Michael Coughlan, 'Undertaking a Literature Review: A Step-by-Step Approach' [2008] 17(1) *British Journal of Nursing* 38, 39.

³⁵ Ibid 38; NT Hong Bui, 'Methodology of the Literature Review: A Comparison of Systematic Literature Review and Narrative Literature Review' [2021] 9(12) *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management* 367-371.

³⁶ Jamie L Callahan, 'Constructing a Manuscript: Distinguishing Integrative Literature Reviews and Conceptual and Theory Articles' [2010] 9(3) *Human Resource Development Review* 300-304.

³⁷ Jamie L Callahan, 'Writing Literature Reviews: A Reprise and Update' [2014] 13(3) *Human Resource Development Review* 271-275.

³⁸ UE Chigbu, SO Atiku and CC Du Plessis, 'The Science of Literature Reviews: Searching, Identifying, Selecting and Synthesizing' [2023] 11(2) *Publications* 1-16.

³⁹ IS Mohammed, 'Problems of Academic Literature Review and Writing: The Way Forward' [2018] 16(5) *Journal of Management Sciences* 11, 17.

⁴⁰ Cynthia Grant and Azadeh Osanloo, 'Understanding, Selecting and Integrating a Theoretical Framework in Dissertation Research: Creating the Blueprint for Your "House"' [2015] 4(2) *Administrative Issues Journal* 12, 16-17.

⁴¹ C James, 'Effective Writing for Lawyers' (2014) 13 <<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/267327816>> accessed 20 May 2018.

For example, in a study on ‘Compensation for Land Compulsorily Acquired for Petroleum Operations in Nigeria’, the researcher has to isolate at least four concepts for review. These are: Concept of Compensation; Concept of Land; Concept of Compulsory Acquisition; and Concept of Petroleum Operations. In a study on ‘Abuse of Fundamental Human Rights by Employers in Nigeria’, the research has to review at least four concepts, viz.: Concept of Abuse; Concept of Right; Concept of Human Rights; and Concept of Fundamental Rights.

7.2 Theoretical Framework

The **theoretical framework** deals with the jurisprudential basis of the research. It identifies and explains two or more theories of law and how they apply to the research. A theory is a systematic organization of knowledge which can be applied for the purpose of solving a problem.⁴² Accordingly, the theoretical framework is ‘a structure that guides research by relying on a formal theory constructed by using an established, coherent explanation of certain phenomena and relationships’.⁴³

The theoretical framework consists of the selected theory or theories that undergirds your thinking with regards to how you understand your topic and the concepts and definitions from the selected theory or theories that are relevant to your topic. Thus, in order to construct a theory, it is necessary to define its basic concepts and to explain how these concepts relate to each other.⁴⁴ For example, to use the positivist theory in research, the researcher has to explain the concept of command and the concept of sovereignty and their relationship to each other and to the subject matter of the research.

A theoretical framework serves several purposes. It shows how the research study is related to the work of others. It also makes clear how the research study is related to one or more scholarly traditions or theories of law.⁴⁵ There are two main **types of theories** in legal research. These are general theories and special theories.

(a) General Theories

General theories are those propounded by the various schools of jurisprudence. They include the positivist theory, realist theory, natural law theory, Marxist theory, sociological theory and historical theory.⁴⁶ A researcher must base his research study on at least one or more general theories before considering any special theory or theories applicable to his study.

(b) Special Theories

Special theories are those that apply to different themes or subject areas. They are also known as thematic theories. Examples include feminist theory, social contract theory, neo-liberal theory, equity theory, critical theory, monist theory, dualist theory, automatic theory, elective theory, Hohfeld’s theory, systems theory, utilitarian theory, behaviourist theory, queer theory, gender theory, transactional theory, postcolonial theory, constructivist theory, etc.⁴⁷

Under the NALT Guide, the **historical foundation**, also called **historical background** or **historical development** of the subject matter, is also discussed after the theoretical framework.⁴⁸ This enables the researcher to introduce some historical perspective into the research. It enables the researcher to take into account the legislative history of the subject matter or the forces that have shaped the law up to the present time. The past is always a preface to the present.⁴⁹

⁴² Jason Thomas, ‘Scholarly Views on Theory: Its Nature, Practical Application and Relation to World View in Business Research’ [2017] 12(9) *International Journal of Business and Management* 231-240, 232.

⁴³ M Eisenhart, ‘Conceptual Frameworks for Research: Ideas from a Cultural Anthropologist; Implications for Mathematics Education Researchers’ (Proceedings of the Thirteenth Annual Meeting of the North American International Group for the Psychology of Mathematics Education, Blacksburg, Virginia, USA, 1991) 205.

⁴⁴ Sanne Taekema, ‘Theoretical and Normative Frameworks or Legal Research: Putting Theory into Practice’ in *Law and Method* (Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam 2018) 3.

⁴⁵ See generally Nasir Mojeed, MA Muktar and MI Ehsan, ‘Theoretical and Conceptual Frameworks in Social Sciences and Law: Meaning, Functions and Differences’ [2023] 5(1) *Pakistan Journal of Social Research* 147, 153-154; Rhuks Ako, ‘Methodology, Theoretical Framework and Scholarly Significance: An Overview of International Best Practices in Legal Research’ [2017] 8(2) *Afe Babalola University Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy* 225, 237-238.

⁴⁶ See generally Shanker S Prasad, ‘Schools of Jurisprudence: A Critical Study’ [2019] 6(3) *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research* 616-623.

⁴⁷ See generally Robert Cyer and others, *Research Methodologies in EU and International Law* (Hart Publishing 2011) 1-75.

⁴⁸ NALT Gide (n 3) 29-30.

⁴⁹ PM Bakshi, ‘Legal Research and Law Reform’ in SK Verma and MA Wani, *Legal Research and Methodology* (2nd edn, Indian Law Institute 2001) 111, 123.

7.3 Empirical Framework

The **empirical framework** deals with the review of previous studies carried out by others on the research topic or an aspect of the research topic or something close to it. It does not mean a review of empirical studies in the sense of empirical or experimental research. It simply means the **review of related literature** on the subject matter.

8.0 Process of Literature Review

There are four critical stages involved in the process of literature review. These are literature searching, literature classification, literature critiquing and analyzing gap in knowledge. It is intended to examine each of them in some detail.

8.1 Literature Search

Literature search is a comprehensive exploration of both published and unpublished sources of literature with the aim of identifying, locating and retrieving previous scholarly works on a research topic. It is the first major step in the process of literature review.⁵⁰

A good researcher should begin the literature review process by carrying out preliminary reading on the research topic to gain familiarity with the research topic, terminologies, keywords, key concepts, theories and methodologies. These variables will be useful in identifying, locating and retrieving relevant literature on the research topic.

There are two main **search techniques** for identifying, locating and retrieving relevant materials on the research topic. These are manual search and electronic search. A further search technique that is supplementary to them is citation search, also known as snowball search.⁵¹ It is intended to examine each of them in some detail.

(a) Manual Search:

Manual search, also known as traditional search, is conducted in a traditional or physical library with the aid of a library catalogue or index card, which gives bibliographic information on the library holdings. The library catalogue or index card lists all the books, journals and other publications by title, location, key ideas and shelf number of the library for easy retrieval.⁵² It is used with the list of shelves to locate and retrieve a particular book, journal article or other publication.

(b) Electronic Search:

Electronic search is conducted on the internet with the aid of an electronic device such as a computer or phone. There are two main types of electronic search. These are web (or website) search and database search. Both web search and database search are done by prompting the electronic device with keywords, key concepts or authors, or a combination of two or more variables. Thus, the use of appropriate keywords is the cornerstone of an effective electronic search.⁵³

Web search is conducted with the aid of search engines prominent amongst which are Scopus, Yahoo, Chrome, Edge, Google, Google Books and Google Scholar.⁵⁴ These search engines are free but, like databases, some of the materials on the website can be accessed only upon payment of subscription fee or specified charge.

However, there is an “open access” initiative which has emerged as an alternative to the traditional subscription-based journal publishing. It permits users to read, download, copy, distribute and print the full texts of articles or use them for any other lawful purpose without financial, legal or other barriers other than those associated with gaining access to the internet itself.⁵⁵

Database search is conducted on structured data sources such as digital libraries. Most databases are searchable collections of journal, magazine and newspaper articles. Some data bases provide the full

⁵⁰ Tallie Casucci and Barbara Wilson, ‘How to Conduct a Literature Search’ in E Day, E LeMonnier and T Casucci (eds), *What is Evidence-Based Practice?* (Utah Education Network Digital Press 2025) <<http://doi.org/10.26052/d-m9kj-gwec>> accessed 4 March 2026.

⁵¹ Andrea Heath, Paul Levay and Daniel Tuvey, ‘Literature Searching Methods or Guidance and Their Application to Public Health Topics: A Narrative Review’ [2021] *Health Information and Library Journal* 1-15.

⁵² F Timmins and C McCabe, ‘How to Conduct an Effective Literature Search’ [2005] 20(11) *Nursing Standard* 41, 43.

⁵³ Ibid 44.

⁵⁴ Terry Hutchinson, ‘Vale Bunny Watson? Law Librarians, Law Libraries and Legal Research in the Post-Internet Era’ [2014] 106(4) *Law Library Journal* 579, 588.

⁵⁵ Arslan Sheikh and Joanna Riochardson, ‘Open Access Movement in the Scholarly World: Pathways for Libraries in Developing Countries’ [2023] *Journal of Information Sciences* 1-19.

text of articles while others provide only abstracts or summaries.⁵⁶ Some databases have specialized subject holdings such as law, medicine, engineering and social sciences. Databases are made available to end users through an intermediary organization known as online service.⁵⁷

Examples of foreign online legal databases include Academia, ResearchGate, FindLaw, Justia, Juta Law, Westlaw, Hein Online, LexisNexis and JSTOR.⁵⁸ Examples of Nigerian online legal databases include Legalpaedia, Law Pavillion, Nigerian Legal Information Institute (NigerianLII), Law Companion and vlex Nigeria. However, Wikipedia is not an authoritative source of literature for legal research as materials on Wikipedia are not validated through peer review.⁵⁹

(c) Citation Search:

Citation search is a supplementary technique for locating further literature through works cited in a relevant article. It is also known as snowballing technique. It essentially involves reviewing the footnotes, bibliographies and references in a recent and relevant article for additional articles.⁶⁰ Thus, the footnotes, bibliographies and references in current and relevant books, journal articles, seminar papers, conference papers, theses and dissertations provide useful guides to other relevant literature.

8.2 Literature Classification

After identifying, locating and retrieving relevant literature, the next step in the process of literature review is for the researcher to classify and organize the relevant literature into different themes or variables in the research topic.⁶¹ The literature can be arranged by grouping them on the basis of similarities in concepts or theories, methodological similarities, or the historical development of the subject matter.⁶² The literature can also be arranged on the basis of subject matter or other variables in the literature.

In a research proposal, for example, the researcher could classify the literature into concepts, theories and empirical studies (or previous studies) on the research topic. This will help the researcher to fully review the literature under conceptual framework, theoretical framework and empirical framework (or review of related literature) in chapter two of the thesis or dissertation. That is why, with little additions and adjustments, a researcher could transform the research proposal into the first two chapters of his thesis or dissertation.

In a thesis or dissertation on 'Abuse of Fundamental Rights in Nigeria', for example, the researcher could classify the literature into right to life, right to movement, right to fair trial, right to dignity, etc. Alternatively, he could classify the literature into abuse of fundamental rights by police, abuse of fundamental rights by employers, abuse of fundamental rights by administrative agencies, etc.

8.3 Literature Critiquing

Many a researcher sees the literature review as a bibliographic summary of the existing literature on the research topic. However, the literature review should not be just a bibliographic summary of previous studies on the research topic.⁶³ The researcher should undertake a critical review of the

⁵⁶ Benedictine University Library, 'Searching a Database' <www.researchguides.ben.edu> accessed 7 March 2026.

⁵⁷ S Blair Kauffman, 'Electronic Databases in Legal Research: Beyond Lexis and Westlaw' [1987] 13 *Rutgers Computer & Technology Law Journal* 73, 74.

⁵⁸ S Sunandini, 'Legal Research: Use of Techniques, Tools and Evolving Technology' [2022] 5(1) *International Journal of Law Management & Humanities* 159, 166-167.

⁵⁹ Diana Ridley, *The Literature Review: A Step-by-Step Guide for Students* (2nd edn, Sage Publications Ltd 2012) 46; A Bolderston, 'Writing an Effective Literature Review' [2008] 39 *Journal of Medical Imaging and Radiation Sciences* 86, 88.

⁶⁰ Tallie Casucci and Barbara Wilson, 'How to Conduct a Literature Search' in E Day, E LeMonnier and T Casucci (eds), *What is Evidence-Based Practice?* (Utah Education Network Digital Press 2025) <<http://doi.org/10.26052/d-m9kj-gwec>> accessed 4 March 2026.

⁶¹ Patricia Cronin, Frances Ryan and Michael Coughan, 'Undertaking a Literature Review: A Step-by-Step Approach' [2008] 17(1) *British Journal of Nursing* 38, 40; Diana Ridley, *The Literature Review: A Step-by-Step Guide for Students* (2nd edn, Sage Publications Ltd 2012) 100.

⁶² American Psychological Association, *Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association: The Official Guide to APA Style* (7th edn, American Psychological Association 2020) 8.

⁶³ David N Boote and Penny Beile, 'Scholars Before Researchers: On the Centrality of Dissertation Literature Review in Research Preparation' [2005] 34(6) *Educational Researcher* 3, 4.

existing literature on the research topic. The researcher should critically analyze, evaluate and synthesize the literature with the objectives of the present study in mind.⁶⁴

At this stage, the researcher should analyze each of the previous studies by deconstructing it and identifying the most relevant information in it. He should also evaluate the literature by comparing, contrasting and appraising the methods, claims, analyses and findings of the previous studies. He should further synthesize all the available literature to get an overall picture of the state of knowledge on the research topic and derive conclusion from the existing literature.⁶⁵

In critiquing the literature on the research topic, the researcher should pay attention to the research methodology adopted by each scholar, the main concepts and theories used to explain the subject matter of the research, the methods and procedures for collecting and analyzing the data, the scope of the study and the findings.⁶⁶ This will enable the researcher to determine the areas of consensus, the areas of disagreement in the existing studies that have generated current debate in the field and the areas that have not been adequately addressed in the exiting literature.⁶⁷ The researcher can then reach a judgement about the key findings that appear to be valid and those that can be contested in the existing literature and demonstrate how his research is different from the previous studies.⁶⁸

8.4 Analyzing Gap in Knowledge

The final stage in the process of literature review is analyzing the gap in knowledge. The **gap in knowledge** is the missing link in the body of knowledge in a particular field. It is the lack of knowledge or understanding of an issue. To put it in simple arithmetic, the gap in knowledge is the difference between the existing body of knowledge and what is still required to reach any conclusion or make any decision on any issue.⁶⁹

In fact, identifying a gap in knowledge and setting out to fill the gap are the most crucial steps in scientific research. It is the gap in knowledge the researcher fills that makes original contribution to existing body of knowledge. In other words, it is the identification of a gap in knowledge that presents the researcher with the opportunity for new research.⁷⁰

The gap in knowledge could be unresolved conflicting decisions of the appellate courts or unresolved conflicting pieces of legislation. It could also be paucity of literature on an important issue. It could further be an unresolved problem in the implementation of any law or decision of a court. Finally, it could be an important issue that has not been adequately addressed in previous studies; or an important issue that was overlooked or ignored in the existing literature; or an outdated explanation on an issue which is no longer relevant and, therefore, needs to be updated.⁷¹

The researcher should critically appraise the existing literature and clearly state the gap which he intends to fill by carrying out the research. It is the identification of a gap in knowledge that will help the researcher to formulate the research problem.⁷²

9.0 Conclusion and Suggestions

⁶⁴ HR Maier, 'What Constitutes a Good Literature Review and Why Does Its Quality Matter?' [2013] 43 *Environmental Modelling & Software* 3-4.

⁶⁵ JE Dodgson, 'Critical Analysis: The Often-Missing Step in Conducting Literature Review Research' [2021] 37(1) *Journal of Human Lactation* 27-32.

⁶⁶ Jill Jesson and Fiona Lacey, 'How to Do (or Not to Do) a Critical Literature Review' [2006] 6(2) *Pharmacy Education* 139-148.

⁶⁷ Marco Pautasso, 'Ten Simple Rules for Writing a Literature Review' [2013] 9(7) *PLOS Computational Biology* 1, 3; Jeffrey W Knopf, 'Doing a Literature Review' [2006] 39(1) *Political Science and Politics* 127, 129-130.

⁶⁸ See MNK Saunders and C Rojon, 'On the Attributes of a Critical Literature Review' [2011] 4(2) *Coaching: An International Journal of Theory, Research and Practice* 156-162; HR Maier, 'What Constitutes a Good Literature Review and Why Does Its Quality Matter?' [2013] 3-4 *Environmental Modelling and Software* 3.

⁶⁹ HA Abass, BA Hassan and AJ Abosede, 'Research Gaps: Sources and Methods of Identification' [2022] <<http://www.researchgate.net/338376635>> accessed 16 August 2024.

⁷⁰ MN Ajemba and EC Arene, 'Research Gaps for Future Research and Their Identification' [2022] 16(01) *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews* 575-579.

⁷¹ JW Knopf, 'Doing a Literature Review' [2006] 39(1) *Political Science and Politics* 127, 130.

⁷² Isaiah Baako and others, 'Understanding and Spotting Research Gaps through a Systematic Literature Review' [2022] 6(3) *International Journal of Research and Innovations in Social Sciences* 549, 551.

A review of related literature is central to any research. It helps the researcher to be abreast with state-of-the-art knowledge of the topic. It also acquaints the researcher with the main concepts, theories, methodologies, methods, findings and current debates in the research area.⁷³ However, nowadays literature reviews are poorly written as annotated bibliographies without any analysis of the relationship amongst the existing literature, evaluation of their strengths and weaknesses and synthesis of the findings and contributions of other scholars to the research topic. Most researchers see the literature review as mere descriptive summaries of literature without conducting any deeper analysis.⁷⁴ It is against this background that this paper suggests that researchers should conduct literature review at two levels to produce quality research reports. Firstly, they should conduct a preliminary literature review to widen and deepen their knowledge of the subject area to enable them find an appropriate and valid research topic, discover gaps and anomalies in the existing literature and raise pertinent questions that will guide the main research. Secondly, they should conduct a thorough literature review by analyzing, evaluating and synthesizing the existing literature on the research topic and thereby make meaningful contribution to knowledge.

⁷³ JJ Randolph, 'A Guide to Writing the Dissertation Literature Review' [2009] 14(3) *Practical Assessment Research and Evaluation* 1, 2.

⁷⁴ Hannah Snyder, 'Literature Review as a Research Methodology: An Overview and Guidelines' [2019] 104 *Journal of Business Research* 333, 338.